

Synthesis and study of new mesogenic homologous series : 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-bromobenzenes

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A new homologous series of liquid crystals viz. 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-bromobenzenes comprising of twelve mesogens have been synthesized. It is a high melting series of mesogens. The nematic type mesophase commences from the very first member of the series. Smectic and nematic mesophases are exhibited by tenth homologue. Dodecyl, tetradecyl and hexadecyl derivatives are purely smectogenic. Nematic mesophase shows threaded texture while smectic mesophase shows focal conic fan shaped texture. The usual odd-even effect is observed in nematic-isotropic transition curve. The smectic-isotropic transition curve rises gradually and falls smoothly at the hexadecyl homologue. The mesomorphic range is wide. The thermal stability and mesomorphic characteristics are compared with structurally similar homologous series.

A new homologous series with -COO- and -N=N- central linkages viz. azo ester homologous series has been synthesized and its mesomorphic properties compared with other similar series¹.

Results and discussion

4-Hydroxy-3-methylphenylazo-4'-bromobenzene is a nonliquid crystal substance but addition of benzene ring bridged through -COO- and left *n*-alkoxy terminal increases the length of the molecules enhancing lateral attractions and polarizability. Homologous series 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-bromobenzenes is a high melting series of mesogens. Methyl to octyl derivatives of the series show very sharp solid-nematic transitions at definite temperatures and smoothly transform into isotropic liquid. Transition temperatures are given in Table 1. The nematic-isotropic transition shows smooth descending tendency as the series is ascended. Alternation of transition temperatures is due to odd-even effect. The solid mesomorphic transition shows a smooth downtrend for alkyl chains having upto eight carbon atoms in the chain, thereby rises once again before showing a final downward trend. The mesomorphic range is high and gradually decreases as series is ascended. The nematic-isotropic transition temperatures are relatively high which may be due to the presence of strong terminal attractions caused by bromo (-Br) group and *n*-alkoxy group bonded in a similar position affecting the ratio of lateral to terminal attractions. Moreover, presence of -N=N- unit with phenyl ring can raise the transition temperature.

Liquid crystals of moderate chain lengths yields only nematogenic homologues². But by increasing the alkyl chain length, smectic property is induced at the cost of nematic property. Hence tenth homologue is polymesomorphic³ and only smectogenic character is exhibited by twelfth, fourteenth and sixteenth member of the title series⁴.

Table 1. Transition temperatures of the homologous series
4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-bromobenzenes

<i>n</i> -Alkyl group	Transition temp. in °C		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
Methyl	-	166.0	207.0
Ethyl	-	148.0	224.0
Propyl	-	130.0	209.0
Butyl	-	123.0	203.0
Pentyl	-	114.0	186.0
Hexyl	-	92.0	177.0
Heptyl	-	97.0	164.0
Octyl	-	89.0	161.0
Decyl	94.0	132.0	150.0
Dodecyl	108.0	-	141.0
Tetradecyl	115.0	-	143.0
Hexadecyl	103.0	-	124.0

Table 2. Average thermal stabilities in °C

Series	(I)	(A)	(B)	(C)
Nematic-isotropic	191.37 (C ₁ -C ₈)	231.1 (C ₁ -C ₁₀)	199.0 (C ₃ -C ₁₀)	152.14 (C ₁ -C ₇)
Smectic-nematic or	135.0 (C ₁₀ -C ₁₆)	149.7 (C ₆ -C ₁₆)	122.0 (C ₁₂ -C ₁₆)	114.66 (C ₇ -C ₁₆)
Smectic-isotropic Commencement of smectic mesophase	C ₁₀	C ₆	C ₁₂	C ₇

Table 3. Elemental analysis for 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-bromobenzenes

Homologue	Molecular formula	Found (%)			Calcd. (%)		
		C	H	N	C	H	N
Methyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ Br	59.35	4.12	6.51	59.29	4.00	6.58
Ethyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ Br	60.02	4.45	6.72	60.13	4.32	6.37
Propyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₃ Br	60.57	4.88	6.91	60.92	4.63	6.18
Butyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₃ Br	60.60	4.97	5.22	61.67	4.92	5.99
Pentyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₃ Br	62.02	5.21	5.70	62.37	5.19	5.82
Hexyl	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₃ Br	62.85	5.40	5.57	63.03	5.45	5.65
Heptyl	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ N ₂ O ₃ Br	63.42	5.72	5.32	63.65	5.69	5.50
Octyl	C ₂₈ H ₃₁ N ₂ O ₃ Br	64.16	5.90	5.18	64.24	5.92	5.35
Decyl	C ₃₀ H ₃₅ N ₂ O ₃ Br	65.19	6.40	5.02	65.33	6.35	5.08
Dodecyl	C ₃₂ H ₃₉ N ₂ O ₃ Br	66.22	6.78	4.72	66.32	6.73	4.83
Tetradecyl	C ₃₄ H ₄₃ N ₂ O ₃ Br	67.04	7.15	4.36	67.21	7.08	4.61
Hexadecyl	C ₃₆ H ₄₇ N ₂ O ₃ Br	68.12	7.45	4.16	68.03	7.40	4.40

Alternation in nematic-isotropic transition curve from first to the tenth homologue is observed due to the extension of shorter alkyl chains along an axis determined by the tetrahedral bond angles. The nature of the contact between terminal (*n*-alkoxy) groups of molecules arranged at end to end will then differ for even and odd homologues. This affects the terminal interactions between molecules. The longer chain may be constrained in case of higher homologues to lie in line with the major axis of the core resulting into end to end contact same for odd and even homologues. This also results into disappearance of alternation of transition temperatures with increasing tendency of the *n*-alkyl chain to bend. Also the odd-even effect in smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic curve is absent in case of members of the series beyond tenth because all the members beyond tenth are of even numbered members.

The present homologous series (I) is compared with other homologous series (A), (B) and (C)⁵ for their molecular characteristics and thermal stabilities as given in Table 2.

4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-methyl benzenes⁵

Conclusions :

A new homologous series of mesogens with -COO- and -N=N- central bridges is synthesized by treating 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl) chlorides with 4-hydroxy-3-methyl phenyl azo-4'-bromobenzene. The order of smectic efficiency is : (i) -H > -CH₃, (ii) -Br > -COCH₃ > -CH₃.

Experimental

4-Hydroxy-3-methylphenylazo-4'-bromobenzene was prepared by reacting *o*-cresol and *p*-bromoaniline by usual method. The azo dye formed was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized in glacial acetic acid till it gave constant melting point. Yield is 64.78%.

p-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyl chlorides were reacted with azo dye to form azo esters. Azo esters were purified in alcohol. Analytical data (Table 3) confirmed the structure. Transition temperatures are recorded in Table 1.

The transition temperatures (Table 1) of the members of the title homologous series were observed through a Laborlux polarizing microscope provided with a Kofler heating stage.

Note

¹H NMR 4-(4'-n-octyloxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-bromobenzene : (200 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) 0.897 (t, CH₃-CH₂ of C₈H₁₇), 1.303, 1.319, 1.442, 1.473 (q, CH₃-CH₂ of C₈H₁₇), 1.736–1.898 (m, (CH₂)_n), 2.332 (s, CH₃-Ar), 4.021 (t, O-CH₂-CH₂ of C₈H₁₇), 6.971 and 7.015, 7.258 and 7.321 (dd, *p*-sub.), 7.624–7.853 (m, tri sub.), 8.012, 8.152 and 8.188 (dd, *p*-sub.).

¹H NMR 4-(4'-n-tetradecyloxybenzoyloxy)-3-methylphenylazo-4''-bromobenzene : (200 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) 0.88 (t, CH₃-CH₂ of C₁₄H₂₉), 1.27 (s, (CH₂)_n) of C₁₄H₂₉), 1.47 (t, -CH₂-), 1.76 (quin., CH₂-CH₂-CH₂O of C₁₄H₂₉), 2.33 (s, CH₃-Ar), 4.05 (t, O-CH₂-CH₂ of OC₁₄H₂₉), 6.97 and 7.02, 7.26 and 7.32, 7.62 and 7.67, 7.78 and 7.83 (dd, *p*-sub.), 8.15–8.20 (m, tri sub.).

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